

Lignans and Alkaloids of *Talauma hodgsoni*

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Three tetrahydrofurofuranoid lignans viz., (+)-sesamin (I), (+)-fargesin (II) and (+)-pinoresinol dimethyl ether (III), and an oxoaporphine alkaloid viz., lanuginosine (IV) along with β -sitosterol have been isolated from the leaves of *Talauma hodgsoni*. The root bark of the plant furnished lanuginosine and liriodenine (V) (an oxoaporphine alkaloid) and β -sitosterol and the tree bark, lanuginosine and β -sitosterol.

THE genus *Talauma* (Fam: Magnoliaceae) comprises about 15 species of trees or shrubs, natives of East Asia, South America and Japan¹. Up till now only one *Talauma* species, viz., *T. mexicana*, the leaves of which are used as a cardioactive drug² and heart stimulant^{3,4}, has been chemically investigated to yield a new benzylisoquinoline alkaloid, viz., aztequine³ and three neutral constituents, viz., *p*-hydroxybenzophenone⁴, trisemic acid⁴ and *d*-quercitol⁴ from the leaves, and costunolide, a mixture of two sterols and two coloured compounds from the bark⁵. In the present paper we report the chemical investigation of another *Talauma* species, viz., *T. hodgsoni* H.f. and T¹, a lofty evergreen tree growing in the forests of Sikkim Himalayas and Khasia hill at an altitude of 1200-1500 m.

Extensive chromatography of the different fractions of the extractives of *T. hodgsoni*, collected from Darjeeling, resulted in the isolation of three tetrahydrofurofuranoid lignans viz., (+)-sesamin (I)⁶ (yield 0.025%), (+)-fargesin (II)⁷ (0.011%) and (+)-pinoresinol dimethyl ether (III)⁸ (0.1%) and an oxoaporphine alkaloid, viz., lanuginosine (IV)^{9,9} (0.006%) along with β -sitosterol (0.007%) from the leaves, while the root bark furnished lanuginosine (0.005%), liriodenine (V)^{9,10} (0.004%) (oxoaporphine alkaloid) and β -sitosterol (0.005%); the tree bark

afforded lanuginosine (0.005%) and β -sitosterol (0.004%). The present isolation of (+)-fargesin constitutes its second occurrence in nature, the first isolation being from the flower buds of *Magnolia fargesii*⁷. Although the relative configuration of (+)-fargesin was settled⁷ as II, its absolute configuration still remains to be settled.

(+)-Sesamin was identified by direct comparison (co-TLC, IR and Mass spectra) with an authentic sample of (-)-sesamin¹¹. Structures of the two other lignans, (+)-fargesin (II) and (+)-pinoresinol dimethyl ether followed from their optical and spectral data (UV, IR, PMR and MS) (*vide* Experimental) which corresponded well with those reported in the literature⁷. Lanuginosine (IV) and liriodenine (V) and β -sitosterol were also identified by direct comparison with the respective authentic samples.

Experimental

Extraction

Dried and powdered leaves (450 g) of *Talauma hodgsoni* were soxhletted with petroleum ether (60°-80°) and CHCl_3 respectively; while the root bark (500 g) and tree bark (450 g) were soxhletted with CHCl_3 . Each of the extracts was separated into basic and neutral fractions in the usual way.

Each of the neutral isolates was chromatographed over silica gel and the basic portions over Brockman alumina (neutral grade), elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity.

Neutral Constituents

(+)-*Sesamin* (I): The residue obtained from the benzene eluate fractions of the main chromatogram of the neutral portion of the petroleum ether extract of the leaves on rechromatography afforded (+)-sesamin (I), crystallising from petroleum ether- CHCl_3 mixture in colourless needles (yield 0.005%), m.p. 121-122°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +62.1^\circ$ (c 0.84, CHCl_3).

Benzene eluate fractions of the neutral part of the CHCl_3 extract of the leaves on similar treatment afforded an additional amount of (+)-sesamin (yield 0.02%).

(+)-*Fargesin* (II): Benzene- CHCl_3 (1:1) eluate fraction of the above main column upon several rechromatographies afforded (+)-fargesin, crystallised from petroleum ether- CHCl_3 mixture as colourless needles (yield 0.004%), m.p. 132-133°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +122.3^\circ$ (c 0.73, CHCl_3); UV: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (log ϵ): 230 (3.84).

283 (3.57); IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}) 1613, 1595, 1504 (aromatic), 1080 (dihydrofuran ring) and 923-O-CH₂-O-PMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 2.90 (1H, *m*, H-1); 4.85 (1H, *d*, *J* = 5 Hz, H-2); 4.43 (1H, *d*, *J* = 7 Hz, H-6); 3.14-3.48 (2H, *m*, H_A-4 and H-5); 3.67-4.0 (2H, *m*, H_B-4, H_A'-8); 4.08-4.17 (1H, *m*, H_B'-8); 3.88 (6H, *s*, two OCH₃); 5.92-O-CH₂-O-6.78-6.92 (6H, *m*, aromatic protons). MS (m/e, % base peak): 370(90.1, M⁺), 340(2), 339(10), 220(4), 219(9.8), 204(12.2), 203(23.7), 194(11), 178(16), 177(48.3), 166(28), 165(43.4), 161(27.1), 151(36), 149(100), 137(9), 135(54.9), 121(13). CHCl₃-extract of the leaves afforded upon chromatography a further amount of (+)-fargesin (yield 0.007%).

(+)-*Pinoresinol dimethyl ether (III)*: The residue obtained from the CHCl₃-MeOH (95 : 5) eluate fractions of the main chromatogram afforded on rechromatography (+)-pinoresinol dimethyl ether (III) (yield 0.055%), crystallised from petroleum ether-CHCl₃ mixture as colourless needles, m.p. 99°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +68.1^\circ$ (c 0.809, CHCl₃); UV: $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (log ϵ): 228(3.98), 280(3.52); IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm^{-1}) 1600, 1585 and 1500 (aromatic), 1055 (dihydrofuran ring); PMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 3.1 (2H, *m*, H-5 and H-1); 3.72-3.98 (2H, *m*, exo-protons at C-8 and C-4); 3.80 (6H, *s*, two OCH₃); 3.82 (6H, *s*, two OCH₃); 4.15-4.4 (2H, *m*, endo-protons at C-8 and C-4); 4.73 (2H, *d*, *J* = 5 Hz, H-6 and H-2); 6.83-6.92 (6H, *m*, aromatic protons); MS (m/e, % base peak): 386 (100, M⁺), 356(2.6), 355(8), 220(8.2), 219(20), 205(12), 194(16), 177(75), 166(4.08), 165(90), 151(66), 138(23), 137(7.5). Neutral portion of the CHCl₃-extract upon similar treatment afforded a further amount of the same lignan (yield 0.045%).

β -*Sitosterol*: Benzene eluate portion of the main chromatogram of the neutral fractions of the leaves (both the petroleum ether and CHCl₃-extracts) and root- and tree-bark (CHCl₃ extracts) afforded β -sitosterol, crystallised from CHCl₃-MeOH in flakes (yield: leaves—0.007%, root bark—0.005% and tree bark—0.004%), m.p., 137°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -34^\circ$ (c 0.62, CHCl₃), acetate m.p. 134°-135°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -37.5^\circ$ (c 0.51, CHCl₃). Identity of β -sitosterol was confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC and IR) with an authentic sample.

Basic Constituents

Lanuginosin (IV): Petroleum ether extract of the leaves was found to be devoid of any basic constituents. The CHCl₃ eluate portion of the basic fraction of the chloroform extract of the leaves afforded an orange coloured residue, crystallising from CHCl₃ as transparent glistening orange crystals (yield 0.006%), m.p. 310°-312° (dec.), M⁺ 305; IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1650 cm^{-1} (conjugated > C = O), 1600, 1560 and 1495 (aromatic) and 950 (-O-CH₂-O-), and was

identified as lanuginosin (IV) by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC [under UV light], IR and Mass spectra) with an authentic sample. Basic fraction of the tree bark on similar treatment afforded the same alkaloid (yield 0.005%).

Liriodenine (V): The basic fraction from the root bark of *T. hodgsoni* showed two close spots under UV light. The constituents could not be separated by chromatography. Repeated fractional crystallisations from CHCl₃ afforded the less soluble compound in pure state which was finally purified by chromatography to yield lanuginosin (IV) (yield 0.0032%), identified by direct comparison. From the mother liquor after removal of lanuginosin another yellow oxoaporphine, liriodenine (V) (yield 0.004%) was isolated as the more soluble component, purified by chromatography over alumina and crystallised from petroleum ether-CHCl₃ mixture as yellow needles, m.p. 282° (dec.); IR: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1660 cm^{-1} (conjugated > C = O), 1495, 1420 (aromatic), 958 and 942 (-O-CH₂-O-). The compound was identified as liriodenine by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC [under UV light] and IR) with an authentic sample.

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